

Methodology For Improving Students' Musical Performance Skills**Ilyosjon Ro‘zimurodov Azamatovich**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the pedagogical and methodological foundations of improving musical performance skills in students studying in higher educational institutions. The research process highlights the effectiveness of modern teaching methods, innovative pedagogical technologies, and individual and differential approaches aimed at developing musical performance. Also, the role of practical exercises in developing students' technical skills, musical thinking, auditory ability, and artistic and creative activity is scientifically and theoretically substantiated. The article emphasizes the importance of using interactive methods, independent learning, and reflective analysis mechanisms in the formation of performing competence.

Keywords: instrumental performance, performing skills, music education, pedagogical methodology, performing competence, individual approach, differential education, practical exercise, musical thinking.

Introduction.

In today's conditions of globalization and the rapid development of digital technologies, the music education system also requires updating in content and methodology. In particular, the issue of forming and improving the skills of musical performance in future music specialists studying in higher educational institutions is emerging as an urgent pedagogical problem. Musical performance is not only a technical skill, but also an integral unity of musical thinking, artistic taste, auditory culture and creative approach. Therefore, the process of developing performing skills should not be limited to traditional classes, but should be enriched with modern pedagogical approaches.

Performing activities in music education play an important role in the student's personal development. The process of playing a musical instrument serves to reveal the student's inner emotional world, form aesthetic views and develop the ability to think independently. At the same time, methodological problems encountered in practical performance classes, insufficient consideration of individual capabilities, and the uniformity of the exercise system hinder the full development of performance skills.

Modern educational requirements require students not only to perform the musical text technically correctly, but also to be able to interpret the work artistically and demonstrate stage culture based on a creative approach. This creates the need to introduce a methodology based on individual, differential and competency-based approaches to the formation of instrumental performance skills. It is precisely such

approaches that allow the student to reveal his inner potential and gradually develop his performance capabilities.

From this point of view, the scientific, theoretical and practical substantiation of the methodology for improving instrumental performance skills in students, the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process are one of the priority tasks of today's music education. This article is aimed at solving these pressing issues and serves to raise the education of musical performance in higher education to a qualitatively new level.

Discussion.

The process of improving students' musical performance skills is a complex and multifaceted pedagogical phenomenon, which is closely related not only to the repetition of technical exercises, but also to personal and creative development. The expected effect can be achieved only if the methodological approaches used in this process are organized in accordance with the individual capabilities, level of musical preparation and creative potential of the student. Therefore, relying on single standard methods in performance education does not meet the requirements of today.

The analysis conducted within the framework of the study shows that traditional teaching methods place more emphasis on technical accuracy, while issues of artistic interpretation, understanding of the musical image and emotional expression are relegated to the background. However, playing an instrument is not just a set of mechanical movements, but also a harmony of thinking, emotions and creative imagination. Ensuring this harmony requires pedagogical sensitivity from the teacher, along with methodological skills. Another important aspect identified during the discussion is the insufficient use of individual and differentiated approaches. Given that each student has different technical training, hearing abilities and psychological characteristics, teaching based on the same system of exercises slows down the development of performing skills. On the contrary, exercises adapted to the student's personal capabilities, a gradually complicated repertoire and tasks aimed at independent work serve to sustainably form performing skills. The results of the discussion also showed that modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods play an important role in the education of instrumental performance. Audio and video analysis, reflective assessment of performance with recording, and the use of ensemble and collective performance elements develop the student's culture of working on himself. In this process, the student is formed not only as a performer, but also as a subject who can analyze his own performance. The discussion shows that improving performing skills should not be limited to classroom training. The methodology, combined with independent learning, creative research, stage experience and concert activities, further strengthens the student's professional competence. Such an approach forms a responsible and conscious attitude of the future music specialist to performing

activities. In general, the results of the discussion mean that the methodology for improving students' instrumental performance skills needs to be revised in accordance with the requirements of modern education. Only a methodological approach aimed at developing technical skills, artistic thinking and creative activity as a whole system can ensure the quality and effectiveness of music education.

Literature analysis.

The issue of developing musical performance skills in students is an important scientific problem studied at the intersection of music pedagogy, performing arts and educational methodology. Research in this area is mainly focused on the mechanisms of formation of performing skills, pedagogical approaches and issues of increasing the effectiveness of practical training.

In classical literature on music pedagogy, the formation of musical performance skills is interpreted on the basis of the unity of technical preparation, musical hearing and artistic thinking. In particular, representatives of Russian and European music-pedagogical schools, evaluating the performance process as a complex psychophysiological and creative activity, emphasize the need to organize the system of exercises on a scientific basis. These studies widely cover the importance of the purposeful selection of technical exercises, work with the repertoire and stage experience.

In Uzbek music pedagogy, the issues of instrumental performance have also been formed as a separate scientific direction. In studies related to national musical traditions, maqom performance, and folk instrument education, the process of forming performing skills is interpreted as being inextricably linked to national musical thinking and aesthetic values. In this literature, the teacher-student tradition, continuity of practical training, and the gradual development of performing experience are indicated as important factors. In scientific sources published in recent years, a competency-based approach to instrumental performance education is being given special attention. Researchers interpret performing competence as a complex set of qualities related not only to technical competence, but also to creative independence, the ability to analyze music, and reflective thinking. This approach is distinguished by the fact that it places the student's personal development at the center of the educational process.

In modern literature, the impact of digital technologies and innovative pedagogical methods on the education of musical performance is also being studied separately. Analysis through audio and video recordings, the use of multimedia tools, and the organization of interactive classes are considered effective factors in developing students' self-control and independent work skills. However, some studies also note that the improper use of technologies can negatively affect the artistic aspects of the performance process.

Conclusion

The analyses and discussions conducted show that improving students' musical performance skills is one of the most important and complex tasks of music education. This process is not limited to the perfect performance of technical exercises, but also requires the integral development of musical thinking, artistic taste, auditory culture, and creative activity. Therefore, the need for a comprehensive and systematic approach to performance education is clearly evident.

The results confirm that the methodology based on individual and differential approaches in the formation of instrumental performance skills is highly effective. Classes organized taking into account the student's personal capabilities, psychological characteristics and level of preparation serve the stable and gradual development of performing skills. In this regard, the combination of traditional teaching methods with modern pedagogical technologies is of great importance.

Also, the use of interactive methods, reflective analysis and elements of independent learning in the process of practical classes forms a conscious attitude of students to their own performance. This creates a basis for their development not only as performers, but also as creative thinkers, professional subjects who can work on themselves. In particular, the integration of stage experience and concert activities into the educational process serves as an important factor in strengthening performing competence.

In conclusion, the methodology for improving students' instrumental performance skills should be improved in accordance with the requirements of modern music education. A methodological approach aimed at developing technical mastery, artistic interpretation, and creative independence as a whole system serves to increase the effectiveness of music education and enhance the professional training of future music professionals.

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